

Composition and Stability of Molybdenum (VI)—Quinalizarin Chelate

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The formation of a pinkish violet chelate between hexavalent molybdenum and quinalizarin has been studied in 50% ethanolic medium. The chelate has maximum absorbance at 520 nm. The chelate is stable in the pH range 3 to 6.5. The composition has been studied by three different methods and has been found that one mole of molybdenum reacts with one mole of quinalizarin to form a complex. The stability constant was found by the method of Banerji and Dey and mole ratio method. The values of $\log k$ in 50% ethanolic medium by above two methods are 4.11 ± 0.16 and 4.84 ± 0.00 respectively at 25° and at 5.0 ± 0.1 pH. The average value of free energy of formation calculated from the above two values of $\log k$ is -6.07 ± 0.12 K.cal.

Quinalizarin has been used as a reagent in analytical chemistry for detection and photometric determination of metals. Several workers have determined, zirconium, gallium, thorium, boron, uranium, tin, indium, tantalum, lead, praseodymium, lanthanum and tungsten.

A beautiful pinkish coloured complex is formed between molybdenum and quinalizarin¹. In this communication, a study on the composition and stability of complex has been reported in 50% ethanolic medium at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 .

EXPERIMENTAL

A.R. grade sodium molybdate and BDH reagent grade quinalizarin were used in preparing all solutions.

Measurements of absorbance were carried out with Hitachi Perkin Elmer Uv-Vis spectrophotometer (Model 139) working on 220 v/50 cycles single phase a.c. mains.

The pH of all the solutions was adjusted with a Beckman pH meter.

All measurements were made at 25°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Instantaneous colour formation was observed and the chelate was found stable for more than 48 hrs.

Nature of the complex formed : To find the nature of the complex formed, Vosburgh and Cooper's method² was adopted. Mixtures containing various proportions of molybdenum (VI) and reagent (1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4) were prepared, keeping the volume of ethanol 12.5 ml. and total volume 25 ml. in each case. Absorbance was measured at different wavelengths. The maximum absorbance of complex is at 520 nm, and only one complex was formed under

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2. W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437; 1942, **64**, 1630.

the conditions of study. The maximum absorbance of quinalizarin, under these conditions was found to be at 490 nm.

Stoichiometry of components : As has been stated before, the composition was studied by three different methods.

*Job's Method*³ : Job's method of continuous variation has been adopted for determining the composition of the coloured complex formed. The absorbance of the mixtures and chelating agents were measured at two different wavelengths 540 nm and 560 nm, using both equimolar and non-equimolar solutions adjusting the *pH* to 5.0 ± 0.1 . A representative figure has been shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Determination of composition from absorption spectra studies of equimolar solutions at 540 nm (C = concentration of sodium molybdate).

- A, $C = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ $p = 1$
 B, $C = 0.909 \times 10^{-4}$ $p = 1$
 C, $C = 0.833 \times 10^{-4}$ $p = 1$

*Mole Ratio Method*⁴ : In the determination of the composition by mole ratio method, series of solutions were prepared from equimolar solutions of sodium molybdate and quinalizarin and the mole ratio of reagent to metal was varied from 1 : 0.1 to 1 : 4. The final concentration of quinalizarin was 1.5×10^{-4} M and 1.25×10^{-4} M respectively in two different sets (Fig. 2).

*Slope Ratio Method*⁵ : In the determination by the slope ratio method, the concentration of the variable component was 1×10^{-4} M and final concentration of excess component was 2×10^{-4} M. The *pH* of solutions was maintained at 5.0 ± 0.1 . The *pH* was adjusted by the addition of required amounts of HCl or NaOH as the case may be. The absorbance was observed at 540 and 560 nm.

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The composition, as determined by three different methods, was found to be metal: ligand as 1 : 1.

Fig. 2. Mole ratio method at 540 nm.

Final concentration of quinalizarin A = $1.5 \times 10^{-4} M$

Final concentration of quinalizarin B = $1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$

The chelate was found stable in the pH range 3 to 6.5.

Calculation of stability constant: The stability constant was calculated by the methods of Banerji and Dey⁶ and mole ratio method⁴. The values of $\log k$ in 50% ethanolic medium by above two methods are 4.11 ± 0.16 , 4.84 ± 0.00 at 25° and 5.0 ± 0.1 pH and the average value of free energy charges of formation calculated from the above two values of $\log k$ is -6.07 ± 0.12 K.cal/mole.

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